

QUANTIFYING THE CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS THAT EMERGE DURING THE POLYMER PROCESSING BY A SURFACE DIELECTRIC BARRIER DISCHARGE UTILIZING LIQUID ELECTRODES

Oleksandr GALMIZ^{1,2}, Richard CIMERMAN¹, Zdenko MACHALA¹

¹Department of Environmental Physics, Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics, Comenius University in Bratislava, Mlynská dolina, 842 48 Bratislava, Slovak Republic

*²Department of Plasma Physics and Technology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, 611 37 Brno, Czech Republic
e-mail: oleksandr.galmiz@uniba.sk*

Abstract

In spite of the rapid expansion of low-temperature plasma physics and technology applications, numerous plasma processes remain inadequately comprehended, particularly the physical and chemical interactions occurring between plasmas and solid or liquid substrates. Consequently, it becomes imperative to implement precise diagnostic methodologies to quantify the flow of chemically active species generated during these processes, identify the relevant reaction pathways, customize product formations to suit specific applications, and gain further insight into plasma-induced reactivity.

Prior research has documented the utilization of Surface Dielectric Barrier Discharge (SDBD) configurations, which generate gaseous plasma at the interface with conductive liquids serving as electrodes, for the treatment of hollow dielectric structures, such as polymer tubes [1-3]. Despite the extensive development and application of such discharges for diverse purposes, dedicated experiments under well-defined conditions are required for further insights into the potential possibilities for plasma processing applications, especially for developing material processing technology.

In the presented work, we undertook the measurement and quantification of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS) generated both in the gaseous and liquid phases. We explored their correlations with the power supplied to the reactor, the reactor's configuration, and their temporal evolution. Furthermore, we conducted an examination and quantification of by-products present in the liquid phase, particularly those arising during the processing of specific polymers by the SDBD.

Keywords: surface dielectric barrier discharge, liquid electrodes, RONS

Acknowledgment: This work was supported by Marie S. Curie Action Postdoctoral Fellowship under Horizon Europe with grant agreement number 101066764.

References

- [1] GALMIZ Oleksandr, ZEMÁNEK Miroslav, PAVLIŇÁK David and ČERNÁK Mirko. *J. Phys. D. Appl. Phys.*, 2018. Vol. 51, p. 195201.
- [2] GALMIZ Oleksandr, PAVLIŇÁK David, ZEMÁNEK Miroslav, BRABLRC Antonin and ČERNÁK Mirko. *Plasma Process. Polym.*, 2017. Vol. 14, p. 1600220.
- [3] PAVLIŇÁK David, GALMIZ Oleksandr, ZEMÁNEK Miroslav, and ČERNÁK Mirko. *Plasma Process. Polym.*, 2018. Vol. 15, no 7, p. 1–12.